

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

KPIs Definition and evaluation procedures

D4.1

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2. Background Information

Table 1: technical information

Project Full title		Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies	
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Table 2: List of abbreviations

D	DELIVERABLE
WP	WORK PACKAGE
M	MONTH
RHH	RURAL HERITAGE HUB
RM	ROLE MODEL
R	REPLICATOR
SIA	SYSTEMIC INNOVATION AREA
CCF	COMMUNITY CAPITALS FRAMEWORK
CNH	CULTURAL AND NATURAL HERITAGE
KFP	KNOWLEDGE FACILITATORS PARTNERS
KPI	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

3. Summary

The report “KPIs Definition and evaluation procedures” is a public document of the RURITAGE project, delivered in the context of WP4, Task T4.1: Monitoring System and Assessment Procedures. The objective of WP4 is to provide quantifiable evidences of the potential role of Cultural and natural heritage (CNH) as a driver for sustainable growth. To this aim WP4 will monitor the performance of the deployed regeneration schemes in the six Replicators of the project through selected cross-thematic and multiscale Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and through the implementation of a holistic approach based on Systems Dynamics (SD) for properly assessing the heritage-led regeneration. **This document introduces the relevance of Community Capitals Framework as tool for planning strategic interventions to transform rural areas in sustainable development demonstration ‘laboratories’, through the enhancement of their unique CHN potential.** Their associated set of KPIs can monitor the improvements achieved over the time by the practices and actions of the project. Therefore, a set of indicators for each capital (cultural, natural, social, human, built, and financial) is defined together with the methodology used for their selection. Finally, the report establishes the approach for evaluating each KPI.

This deliverable is a working document for the consortium since it sets the basis for the evaluation approach of RURITAGE. The KPIs proposed in this document will be revised and refined in the M13 after the WP1 is finished and the baseline of Replicators is established in T 1.4. Partners in charge of defining the framework for the analysis of the successful heritage-led interventions (TEC) and assessing the intervention performance (CAR) have been the main authors of the current deliverable. In addition, this framework has been provided during the first months of the project to key partners of the project involved not only in WP4 but also in WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP5 in case something is not suitable for the deployment of the corresponding work packages.

4. Introduction

4.1 Objectives

The task T4.1 aims at developing an integrated evaluation procedure to measure the performance and the impacts related with the implementation of the heritage-led regeneration plans developed and implemented in WP3. More specifically, it will define a wide range of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) related to environmental, social, cultural and economic impact categories and associated technical methodology and tools to measure them. Based on this first framework, this task will develop KPIs to allow a smooth diagnosis of the Replicators' state of the art within Task 1.4. The KPIs will be then re-tailored based on WP1 outcomes in the M13.

The process followed to define the KPIs reported in this deliverable comprises 4 steps (see Figure 1): firstly, the theoretical framework for KPIs has been established regarding Community Capitals and its links to Ruritage Systemic Innovation Areas. Secondly, the impact domains related to the framework have been defined and KPIs for its measurement have been selected. Thirdly, KPIs have been prioritized by Role Models and Knowledge Facilitator Partners using RACER methodology, in order to select the most suitable ones. And finally, changes on Cultural Capitals have been considered as the result of the impacts produced by some of the selected KPIs.

Figure 1 Process for KPIs definition

4.2 Contributions of partners

The following table shows the contributions of the different partners.

PARTICIPANT	CONTRIBUTIONS
TEC	Coordination of the task. Development of the deliverable. First proposal of KPIs. Coordination of the link with WP1.
UNIBO	Participation in the selection process and development of KPIs. Coordination of the link with the whole project.
CARTIF	Participation in the selection process and development of KPIs. Coordination of the link with WP4.
UOP	Participation in the selection process and development of KPIs.

Table 1: Contributions of partners

4.3 Relation to other activities in the project

Concept maps have been used to illustrate the relation among concepts and activities in the project. Concept maps¹ are graphical tools for organizing and representing knowledge. They include concepts, usually enclosed in circles or boxes of some type, and relationships between concepts indicated by a connecting line linking two concepts. Words on the line, referred to as linking words or linking phrases, specify the relationship between the two concepts. Concepts can be defined as a perceived regularity or

¹ <http://cmap.ihmc.us/docs/conceptmap.php> [Online].

pattern in events or objects, or records of events or objects, designated by a label. The label for most concepts is a word, although sometimes other symbols or more than one word is used. Propositions are statements about some object or event in the universe, either naturally occurring or constructed. Propositions contain two or more concepts connected using linking words or phrases to form a meaningful statement.

Figure 2 shows the highest-level concept map for RURITAGE. This map illustrates the hierarchical structure and will be helpful to identify common elements that could be used later during the project. Following the structure, it is possible to generate concepts, e.g. “Key Performance Indicators measure the impact of Heritage-led Rural Regeneration Strategies” or “Monitoring System gets feedback from Rural Heritage Hubs (RHH)”. This graph has been supervised by domain experts and does not pretend to be exhaustive.

KPI identification, as illustrated in this report, is the basis for developing an integrated evaluation procedure to measure the performance and impacts achieved through the implementation of the heritage-led regeneration plans identified in WP3. Within Task 1.4, a smooth diagnosis of the Replicators’ state of the art will be developed, based on this framework, identified KPIs and context information. The CCF has been used also in WP1 to frame the knowledge building.

Next tasks within WP4 will deal with the procedures for collecting, processing and analysing KPI’s data. Task 4.2 will develop on Monitoring Programme implementation, data gathering procedures and data analytics. Not every KPI has the same relevance, so expert advice will be collected to proceed with KPIs’ weight assignment. Task 4.3 and 4.4 will deal with monitoring and co-monitoring, respectively, gathering necessary data for KPI calculation from Replicators and community groups (local and visitor, through participatory tools). Impact evaluation and assessment of the heritage-led regeneration plans on Replicators will be developed in Task 4.5, where each Replicator will obtain a global impact evaluation after its heritage-led strategy implementation is terminated, comparing the results with Replicator’s baseline (Task 1.4) and highlighting main improvements.

Figure 2: RURITAGE high level concept map

5. Overall Approach: Strategy for the evaluation of heritage-led regeneration plans

5.1 Community capitals in rural areas

Rural areas have been defined traditionally by what they lack not what they have, although it could be more empowering to capitalise the resources owned by a community rather than identifying all the resources the community does not have. The Community Capital Framework (CCF) offers a structure to consider and valorise the natural and cultural richness of rural areas as a first step to transform these values in other capitals (human, social, built and financial capitals) since the accumulation of different forms of capital within a community is mutually self-reinforcing (Emery & Flora, 2006).

Natural and cultural capitals on rural areas could be the best opportunity to foster rural development, although other capitals have to be developed jointly (Mikulcak, Haider, Abson, Newig, & Fischer, 2015). It also offers the possibility to capitalise intangible heritage especially rich in rural areas. The richness of cognitive elements, or the way individuals think and behave could be as important for success of a territorial system as the material resources (Capello et al. 2009).

The rural identities shape the rural character of the intangible networks, norms and behaviours and these intangible resources tend to be more localized and immobile (Terluin, 2003) and therefore better preserved in rural areas than in globalised urban environments. This framework, first proposed by Emery and Flora in 2006 has been widely used in fields related with the Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs) and cross-cutting issues considered in RURITAGE: sustainable community development through tourism social entrepreneurship (Aquino, Lück, & Schänzel, 2018), resilience enhancement in rural areas (Straub, Gray, Ritchie, & Gill, 2020), analysis of barriers to rural development (Mikulcak et al., 2015) or designing of community-led regional revitalization projects (Uwasu, Fuchigami, Ohno, Takeda, & Kurimoto, 2018). Specifically, the use of indicator and indexes to measure community capitals have been used for the analysis in farming systems in rural communities (Barrera, De Los Rios, Cruz-Collaguazo, & Coronel-Becerra, 2010) or the sustainability of former mining communities (Winkler, Oikarinen, Simpson, Michaelson, & Gonzalez, 2016).

The main ambition of RURITAGE is the creation of an innovative rural regeneration paradigm based on Cultural and Natural Heritage (CNH), consolidating the role of culture as the fourth pillar of sustainable development and contributing to economic growth, social inclusion and environmental sustainability in rural areas. The RURITAGE paradigm consists of a new understanding of CNH as a peculiarity of European rural areas turning a range of various cultural elements and relationships to a combination of factors driving the development and regeneration of rural areas. In this line, the CCF considers that the growth of all forms of capital (built, natural, social, human, financial and cultural) in a community can create virtuous spirals of development (Emery & Flora, 2006). So, within the project, six capitals are going to be considered: cultural (including intangible heritage), natural, built (including built cultural heritage), social (including political), human and financial as framework to measure the effectivity of the proposed actions and practices as mechanisms of capitals transformation (from the initial stock of capitals to other kind of capitals).

The CCF has been used as a tool for *“implementing and tracking system-level changes in a wide range of community development projects”* (Kline, McGehee, & Delconte, 2019) the link with cultural heritage has been mainly related with tourism and the way that development strategies based on *“heritage tourism”* capitalise CNH as natural, cultural and build capitals.

An analysis about the use of CCF in tourism can be found in Kline et al. (2019). Recent work has pointed out that heritage tourism could have potentially a positive or a negative impact and while improving economic development it could also exacerbate some existing problems (Ghahramani, Mc Ardle, & Fatorić, 2020). RURITAGE expands the usual approach and considers that there are more ways to catalyse rural development through the capitalisation of CNH than the tourism. This approach is in the base of the conception of the SIAs.

The literature already considers nature capital and social capital as important competitive forces for rural areas (Svendsen & Sørensen, 2006) and as being among the few key assets of rural areas (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2006). RURITAGE project add to these two capitals the cultural capital as a key asset for rural areas, especially in the form of intangible cultural heritage and aims to use the built cultural heritage as and assets within the infrastructure capital.

CAPITALS	DESCRIPTIONS	RURITAGE APPROACH
CULTURAL CAPITAL	Cultural capital reflects the way people “know the world” and how they act within it, as well as their traditions and language. Cultural capital influences how creativity, innovation, and motivation emerge and are nurtured.	In the RURITAGE context intangible heritage (rural traditions) is one of the key assets including in this capital that the project aims to capitalise.
NATURAL CAPITAL	Natural capital refers to those assets that abide in a location, including weather, geographic isolation, natural resources, amenities, and natural beauty. Natural capital shapes the cultural capital connected to place	Natural Capital connected with biodiversity and landscape is one of the key assets that rural destinations are traditionally taking advantage of.
BUILT CAPITAL	Built capital refers to housing, transportation infrastructure, telecommunications infrastructure and hardware, utilities, heritage buildings and infrastructure.	Historic built heritage can play a key role in the heritage-led process if it is reused and maintained from a sustainability point of view.
SOCIAL CAPITAL	Social capital reflects the connections among people and organizations or the social “glue” to make things, positive or negative, happen. Bonding social capital refers to those close redundant ties that build community cohesion. Bridging social capital involves loose ties that bridge among organizations and communities. Political capital is included here reflects access to power, organizations, connection to resources and power brokers. Governance and political capital is included here as the ability of people to find their own voice and to engage in actions that contribute to the well-being and development of their community	In RURITAGE social capital is understand as the capacity of the community to build economic development networks, local mobilization of resources, and willingness to consider alternative ways of reaching goals.
HUMAN CAPITAL	Human capital is understood to include the skills and abilities of people to develop and enhance their resources and to access outside resources and bodies of knowledge to increase their understanding, identify promising practices, and to access data for community-building.	In RURITAGE, human capital is improved through practices that contribute to the health, training & education of the population.
FINANCIAL CAPITAL	Financial capital refers to the financial resources available to invest in community capacity-building, to underwrite the development of businesses, to support civic and social entrepreneurship, and to accumulate wealth for future community development	In RURITAGE the financial capital is understood as mean to achieve the growing of the other capitals.

Table 2: Community capitals (Based on (Butler Flora, 2008))

5.2 Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs) for heritage-led rural regeneration and development

One of the innovativeness of the RURITAGE paradigm lies on proposing six Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs), based on evidence from 13 Role Models, integrating the tangible and intangible assets of CNH and allowing the formulation of practices, solutions and strategies which can be replicated in a wide variety of contexts across Europe and beyond and mainstreamed in territorial development policies. The task 1.1 is analysing the successful heritage-led rural regeneration models of 13 Role Models (RMs) from a holistic and multidisciplinary perspective (their objectives, motivation, needs and ways to overcome barriers).

This collected information has allowed the conceptualisation of the different SIAs regarding to their link with CCF. The SIAs are characterised regarding the initial capital that is required (initial capital), the capitals that are necessary to develop (required) and the capitals that are finally obtained (obtained). The following table summarises this analysis for each SIA (the dark and light yellow highlights the most relevant capitals for each SIA):

SIA	DESCRIPTION	CONCEPTUALISATION OF THE SIA THROUGH CAPITALS			
		CAPITALS	INITIAL	REQUIRED	OBTAINED
Pilgrimage	Sustainable and economic growth through heritage routes to sacred and historical places	Cultural	Religious		Broad dissemination of the CH
		Natural	Landscape		Broad dissemination of the NH
		Build	Disperse building CH	Tourism/Transport infrastructure	Improvement of built CH
		Human		Capacity building	Better jobs
		Social		Cross-Region governance	Networking governance
		Financial			Jobs and business opportunities through tourism
Sustainable Local Food Production	Improvement of the economic and environmental sustainability of both tourism and agriculture using food, wine and gastronomy symbolising the place and culture of the destination	Cultural	Gastronomy		Broad dissemination of the CH (gastronomy)
		Natural	Local products		Sustainable agriculture
		Build		Hostelry infrastructure	
		Human		Capacity building	Better jobs
		Social		Collaboration	
		Financial			Jobs through services and industry
Migration	Opportunities for repopulation, growth and potential for rural regeneration through the arrival and inclusion of influx of migrants as a source of new vitality to restore declining villages	Cultural	Gastronomy		Broad dissemination of the CH (Gastronomy)
		Natural	Local products		Sustainable agriculture
		Build		Hostelry infrastructure	
		Human		Capacity building	Better jobs
		Social		Collaboration	
		Financial			Jobs through services and industry
Art and festivals	Job creation, building social connections, self-esteem, and community knowledge	Cultural	Intangible		Cultural enrichment (Arts)
		Natural			

	through festivals related with ancient local traditions and products, open-air art exhibition and landscape museums.	Build Human Social Financial	Infrastructure for the events Human resources for the events Management	New infrastructures/ CH restoration Better jobs Job/Business opportunities
Resilience	Protection against losses along with economic growth and jobs and livelihoods creation, through the enhancement of the role of Cultural and Natural Heritage for building resilience against the dual threats of climate change and disasters	Cultural	Recompilation of local knowledge	Better safeguarding of CH
		Natural	Landscape	Better safeguarding of NH
		Build	Risk knowledge	Better safeguarding of Built Heritage
		Human		Safer conditions
		Social	Stakeholder cooperation	
Financial		Economic development of the area		
Integrated Landscape management	Rural renaissance through participatory landscape management integrated in regional and Smart Specialization strategies	Cultural	Cultural Landscape	CH conservation
		Natural	Natural Landscape	NH conservation
		Build		Knowledge building
		Human		Training
		Social		Collaboration between stakeholders
Financial			Better jobs Networking governance Business and jobs opportunities through tourism	

Table 3: Approach to the RURITAGE SIAs from the Capitals Framework

5.3 Selection of KPIs

The starting point of KPIs definition was the selection done during proposal stage based on previous related projects, regulations and tailor-made procedures, as illustrated by Table 4. This initial selection was used for developing the initial state of the art while developing the project proposal and then fine-tuned once the project began.

Domain	KPI	Evaluation Objective	KPI Source	Evaluation Procedure	Parameters
Cultural Heritage	Heritage significance	Heritage impact assessment of the selected strategies	EFFESUS	Based on EFFESUS	
	Cultural products & services	New cultural products & services	SC5-21b-2017 Call	Tailored procedure	
Social Inclusion	Citizen quality of life	Improvements in citizens' quality of life	CITYKeys, REMOURBAN, CITYFIED, SMARTENCITY	Tailored procedure	Physical & mental wellbeing Air quality Energy poverty reduction
	Citizen engagement	Behavior change due to the different interventions	REMOURBAN	Tailored procedure	
	Social acceptance	Evaluating the acceptance and perception of the citizens	CONCERTO, CITYFIED, R2CITIES	Based on CONCERTO	
	High skilled jobs	Developing talent	SC5-21b-2017 Call	Tailored procedure	Skilled jobs
	Set-up of companies	Start-ups in new productive activities	SC5-21b-2017 Call	Tailored procedure	Number of new companies
	Investment in regeneration	Attracting new investment in the regeneration sector	SC5-21b-2017 Call	Tailored procedure	
Environmental Balance	Environmental sustainability and comfort	Improvement of the energy performance and comfort due to building reuse and maintenance	CONCERTO, CITYKeys, REMOURBAN, R2CITIES, ZeeN	IPMVP	
	LCA	Environmental impact due to interventions from whole life cycle of materials	CML, ReciPe, Cumulative energy demand, Environmental footprint	Standard (simplified)	

Table 4: Initial set of KPIs at submitted proposal.

This first selection was employed to define role models baseline according to the different type of impacts identified. This selection composed by six domains and more than 50 KPIs, was adapted and completed among the Knowledge Facilitators Partners (KFP) based on their expertise. The result from this first fine tuning change the initial domains into seven type of impacts: economic impacts, social impacts, environment impacts, climate impacts, technological impacts, organizational impacts and impacts on health and wellbeing. These impacts were subdivided in more than 30 sub-impacts and more than 60 indicators for its measurement. The next table (Table 5) is the final table sent during data gathering in summer campaigning but includes the new contents (compared with proposal stage) in **bold** and discarded contents strikethrough, to be easily identified:

Type of impacts	I codes	Impacts	Indicators
Social Impacts	ISo1	Integration of different stakeholders	N. of people involved in the HUB (n.)
			N. of people involved in events and activities (n.)
			N. of representatives of the civic society involved (n.)
			N. of companies involved (n.)
			Number of stakeholders involved in the Ruritage Hub (n.)
			Number of stakeholders involved in the process
			Associations and groups of citizens involved (n. and n. of people involved)
			Managed or co-managed by associations or groups of citizens? (y/n)
	N. of public bodies and authorities involved (n.)		
	ISo2	Increase awareness and ownership of cultural heritage, sense of identity	N. of events organised to attract/interact with stakeholders
			N. of indigenous groups/ communities involved
			New events promoted by local authorities (n. and n. of people reached)
			Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level (n. and n. of people reached)
	ISo3	Promote access and fruition of the CNH of the vulnerable groups	no. of crowdfunding campaigns launch
			Number of sites accessible by people with disabilities
			Number of projects addressing people with disabilities (n. of projects, and n. of people involved)
	ISo4	Improve the quality of life of residents	Number of visitors with disabilities
			Increase of the employment rate (%)
	ISo5	Integration of migrants with local resident population	Increase of the number of cultural events
			Number of migrants involved in educational-training programs (n. and %)
			Number of internships for migrants activated
ISo6	Regeneration of micro-communities?	Number of migrants actively engaged in the project and participating to the HUB (n.)	
		<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>	
ISo7	Active engagement of disadvantaged people (elderly, migrants, unemployed)	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>	
ISo8	<i>Other indicators?</i>		
Economic	IEc1	Strengthening the	Number of arrivals (n.)

Impacts	tourism sector	"green tourism packages"	
		GDP of the sector (%)	
		Number of hotels	
		Number of restaurants	
	IEc2	Enlarge the tourism offer and attract different target groups	N. of touristic attractions
			N. of tailored or customizable offers (packages, guided tours, etc.)
			Distribution of the arrivals along the year (% per month)
	IEc3	Increase the visibility of the area and the related products	Brands and labels for local products and services (n.)
			Promotion of the area and related products in national and international tourism events and fairs (n. of events and fair per year)
			Signals and explanation panels help describing the sites and orienteering the visitors (n. of sites, km of routes)
	IEc4	Foster innovation in local business and start-ups (organizational, process and products innovation, etc.)	Number of start-ups and spin-off created
			Number of entrepreneurs younger than 35 years involved
			Number of companies supported in defining new business models and innovative processes of production
...			
IEc5	Employment and valorisation of local traditional skills	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>	
IEc6	Flexibility and re-adaptation over time (of functions)	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>	
IEc7	<i>Other indicators?</i>		
Environmental Impacts	IEEn1	Improving eco-mobility	Existing cycle paths (Km)
			Existing pedestrian/hiking paths (km)
			Existing public transport services (Km, people served)
			Existing shared transport services (bike sharing, car sharing, etc.)
	IEEn2	Promote local business for sustainable production	Use of renewable energy in the local production (% of renewable energy)
			Number of companies and organizations with sustainability certifications and labelling
			Number of organic farms (n. and % of the total)
			Number of shops, restaurants and tourism facilities selling local products (KMO) (n. and % on the total)
	IEEn3	Eco-restoration and retrofitting of buildings, improving their environmental performances	Number of buildings restored/retrofitted with green solutions
			Number of reused buildings
			Number of construction enterprises working in green building sector (n. and %)
	IEEn4	Strengthening the protection of the	Number of eco-restoration of habitats/ natural areas or polluted sites (old factory grounds, mining areas, etc.)
			N. of new protocols/agreement for ecological and environmental protection of sites

		environment (in policies and practices)	Area extent affected by specific regulations/plans for the environment protection
	IEn5	Biodiversity	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>
	IEn6	Reduction of waste/ underuse of resources	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>
	IEn7	Number of endangered species	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>
	IEn8	Number of species with economic value	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>
	IEn9	Surface of areas of medium/ high environmental value	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>
	IEn10	Number/proportion of native species	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>
	IEn11	Number of nature-based interventions in the sites	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>
	IEn12	Number of habitats and ecosystems	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>
	IEn13	Existing ecosystem services	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>
Climate Impacts	ICI1	Reduce the production of CO2 promoting the eco-mobility	Increase of the number of people using public transport
			Increase of the number of people walking or cycling daily
	ICI2	<i>Other indicators?</i>	
Technological Impacts	ITe1	Establish broad-band internet connection in rural areas	Number of people connected (in % on the total, and as absolute value)
			Area covered by broad band internet (in % on the total, and as absolute value)
			Number of CNH sites connected (monuments, museum, parks, etc.)
	ITe2	Digitalization of CNH	Number of webpages (translations, graphic improvement, adding of functionalities)
			New tools developed (apps, webpages, bitcoin systems, etc)
			Number of people reached by through digital tools
			Number of CNH features mapped trough GIS
	ITe3	Improvement of IT skills of citizens (different groups) and professionals (especially in the tourism sector)	Number of people trained (in ICT)
			Number of hours of training (in ICT)
	ITe4	Creation of new products (food, art and crafts, bio-industry...)	Number of new food companies created during the process (n. of companies and n. of employees)
			Number of new art and crafts laboratories created during the process (n. of companies and n. of employees)
			Number of prototypes and services co-created in the HUBs
	ITe5	Process innovation	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>
	ITe6	<i>Other indicators?</i>	

Organizational Impacts	IOr1	Improve the CNH management system of the local authorities (guidelines, training, etc.)	Training course to the public authorities staff (number of hours and of number of people involved)
	IOr2	<i>Other indicators?</i>	Number of publications as recommendation and guidelines provided (n.)
Health & Well-being	IHW1	Access to health services	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>
	IHW2	Access to sport services	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>
	IHW3	Number of people unable to work due to (mental) health related problems	<i>Do you use any indicator in this field? Please describe it:</i>

Table 5: Table send during first data gathering summer campaign

This first selection during the proposal was sent to all Role Models together with the initial data gathering campaigning in WP1 (Summer campaigning) in July 2018 for prioritisation. They were asked to complete the list of indicators reformulating the existing ones if necessary, and also to indicate the relevance of each of the indicators for its case study (selecting from the categories: key indicator, relevant, not relevant, not sure). After the responses of the Role Models to the Summer Campaign (July/November 2018), in which the RM, in addition to giving answer to the required data gathering (see D1.1. RURITAGE Practices Repository), also provided comments regarding the KPIs and their possible upgrading; those different comments and changes were merged, resulting in a complete list of KPIs reclassified according to its link with the different Cultural Capitals (Table 6). This work made also possible to filter and to subcategorize the KPIs facing different aspects and objectives. This list of KPI was finally linked to the Cultural Capital Framework.

Capital	Categories	KPI	Type of impacts
CULTURAL	Stocks of cultural capital	Number of enterprises in the cultural sector	Economic Impact/ Growth
	Increase awareness and ownership of cultural heritage, sense of identity	Number of mentions of CNH in social media, media, press, etc.	Social Impact/inclusion
		Number of users registered in the digital hub or following the social networks (facebook, twitter...)	
		Number of posts in the digital hub	
		Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level	
		Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level (n. and n. of people reached)	Social Impact/inclusion
	Number of crowdfunding campaigns launched	Social Impact/inclusion	
Valorisation of local traditional skills	Number of people trained in traditional skills	Economic Impact/ Growth	
Enlarge the tourism offer and attract different target groups	Number of places involved in the tourism offer	Economic Impact/ Growth	
	Distribution of the arrivals along the year (% per month)	Economic Impact/ Growth	
NATURAL	Stocks of natural capital	Type of ecosystem services	Environmental Impacts /balance
		Number and area of designations	
		Emission of greenhouse gases	Climate Impacts
	Promote local business	Share of renewable energy in gross final energy	Environmental Impacts

	for sustainable production	consumption	/balance
		Number of companies and organizations with sustainability certifications and labelling	Environmental Impacts /balance
		Number of shops, restaurants and tourism facilities selling local products (KMO)	Environmental Impacts /balance
	Strengthening the tourism sector	Number of "green tourism packages"	Economic Impact/ Growth
BUILT	Stocks of built/infrastructure capital	Number of hotspots provided	
		Number of people reached through RURITAGE digital tools	Technological Impacts
		Number of CNH objects mapped trough ATLAS	Technological Impacts
		Number of beds	Economic Impact/ Growth
		Number of restaurants	Economic Impact/ Growth
		Cycle paths (Km)	Environmental Impacts /balance
		Pedestrian/hiking paths (km)	Environmental Impacts /balance
		Share of people served by public transport services	Environmental Impacts /balance
		Number of shared transport services (bike sharing, car sharing, etc.)	Environmental Impacts /balance
	Promote access and fruition of the CNH of the vulnerable groups	Number of sites accessible by people with disabilities	Social Impact/inclusion
	Eco-restoration and retrofitting of buildings, improving their environmental performances	Number of buildings restored/retrofitted	Environmental Impacts /balance
		Number of reused buildings	Environmental Impacts /balance
	Increase the visibility of the area and the related products	Number of brands and labels granted for local products and services	Economic Impact/ Growth
		Number of fairs and tourism events per year related to the promotion of the area and related products	Economic Impact/ Growth
Number of sites or km of routes provided with signals and explanation panels to help describing the sites and orienteering visitors		Economic Impact/ Growth	
SOCIAL	Stocks of social capital	Number of citizens engagement activities and participants	Social Impact/inclusion
		Number per type of stakeholder involved (according to the ones defined in D.3.1)	Social Impact/inclusion
		Number of local associations involved	Social Impact/inclusion
		Number of participants in formal or informal voluntary activities or active citizenship in the last 12 months	Social Impact/inclusion
		Number of immigrants actively engaged in the project and participating to the hub	Social Impact/inclusion

		Number of projects addressing people with disabilities (n. of projects, and n. of people involved)	Social Impact/inclusion	
		Number of disadvantaged people engaged (elderly, migrants, unemployed)	Social Impact/inclusion	
HUMAN	Stocks of human capital	Education	Social Impact/inclusion	
		School dropout	Social Impact/inclusion	
		Health care services	Social Impact/inclusion	
		Human Development Index	Social Impact/inclusion	
		Social protection	Social Impact/inclusion	
		Access to health services	Social Impact/inclusion	
		Access to sport services	Social Impact/inclusion	
	Foster innovation in local business and start-ups (organizational, process and products innovation, etc.)	Set-up and growth of companies	Number of immigrants involved in educational-training programs	Social Impact/inclusion
			Number of internships for immigrants activated	Social Impact/inclusion
			Number of self-employees	Economic Impact/ Growth
	Set-up and growth of companies		Number of internships for students	
		Improvement of IT skills of citizens (different groups) and professionals (especially in the tourism sector)	Number of people trained in IT and tourism (in specific SIA)	Technological Impacts
	Improve the CNH management system of the local authorities (guidelines, training, etc.)		Number of people involved in professional management training course (summer school and master)	Organizational Impacts
			Number of publications as recommendation and guidelines provided	Organizational Impacts
FINANCIAL	Stocks of financial capital	Nights spent at tourist accommodation establishments	Economic Impact/ Growth	
		Year revenues per sector/municipality (in specific SIA)	Economic Impact/ Growth	
		Number of PPPs set and signed	Social Impact/inclusion	
		Unemployment rate (%)	Social Impact/inclusion	
	Foster innovation in local business and start-ups (organizational, process and products innovation, etc.)	Set-up and growth of companies	Number of start-ups and spin-off created / Birth of enterprises	Economic Impact/ Growth
			Number of companies supported in defining new business models and innovative processes of production	Economic Impact/ Growth

Table 6: Merged KPIs selection according to its Cultural Capitals

5.3.1 RACER methodology

In order to select the most suitable KPIs, it has been decided to follow the RACER framework (Science Communication Unit, University of the West of England, 2012), as described in Table 7. It is an evaluation framework developed for assessing the value of scientific tools for use in policy making. RACER is an acronym for:

Relevant	closely linked to the objectives to be reached
Accepted	by staff, stakeholders, and other users
Credible	accessible to non-experts, unambiguous and easy to interpret
Easy	feasible to monitor and collect data at reasonable cost
Robust	not easily manipulated

Table 7: RACER criteria framework

The RACER framework and its sub-criteria have been adapted and simplified to the case of RURITAGE. The base for the evaluation is a framework with two sub-criteria within each RACER category, summing up altogether to 10 issues:

RACER CRITERION	RURITAGE SUB-CRITERION	DESCRIPTION	LEVELS
RELEVANCE	Meaningful	Is the indicator meaningful for RURITAGE objectives?	High/mid/low
	Comparable	Is the indicator comparable across different cases?	Yes/no
ACCEPTED	Previously Used	Has the indicator been previously used?	Yes/no
	Standard	Is it a "standard" indicator?	Yes/no
CREDIBLE	Unambiguous	Are the results unambiguous?	Yes/no
	Clear Methodology	Has the indicator a clear methodology?	Yes/no
EASY	Availability	Are the data easily available?	High/mid/low
	Easy to Calculate	Is the indicator easy to calculate?	High/mid/low
ROBUST	Real Data	Does the indicator use real data or robust estimations?	Real/estimations
	Applicable to Similar Cases	Is it possible to apply the indicator in numerous (similar but different) cases? Has it been used in different circumstances and delivered reasonable results?	Yes/no

Table 8: RACER subcriteria for RURITAGE KPIs

The KFP classified the indicators according to the RACER score. In order to select the final set of KPIs the following criteria have been followed:

- Only indicators with a high meaningful score have been selected
- Only comparable indicators have been selected
- Indicators with low data availability have been discarded
- Indicators no applicable to similar cases have been discarded
- Indicators with a RACER score lower of 50 (out of 100) have been discarded

In the following sections the final list of indicators is described, together with the RACER evaluation results and their evaluation procedures.

6. KPIs and evaluation procedures

The objective of the RURITAGE KPIs is to lay the foundations for mapping the strategies and actions that the replicators are going to implement and to measure how is the impact of these actions in terms of increment in assets across the capitals. RURITAGE KPIs aims to identify and measure the role of CNH in these processes. The following sections describe the final selection of the KPIs and their correspondent evaluation procedure.

6.1 Cultural capital KPIs

The values of the society are reflected in the cultural capital, which can be considered as an indicator to assess sustainability. Cultural capital has the potential to create several benefits, from sustainable consumption and production, to revitalization of areas and social participation and cohesion. The transformation of the cultural capital into social, human and financial capitals is mainly related to creative and cultural activities, tourism, local production, citizenship cohesion and inclusion, providing benefits for local communities. Cultural capital, if properly addressed, is a vector for employment creation and wealth, being a potential for economic growth and sustainable development. At the same time, the maintenance and promotion of cultural values and traditions in a community, has the potential of enhancing citizens engagement and inclusion.

6.1.1 Selection of the KPIs

The following 10 KPIs have been selected following the RACER method (see Table 9):

CAPITAL	KPI	CODES	RELEVANCE		ACCEPTED		CREDIBLE		EASY		ROBUST		RACER Value
			Meaningful	Comparable	Previously Used	Standard	Unambiguous	Clear Methodology	Availability	Easy to Calculate	Real Data	Applicable to Similar Cases	
CULTURAL	Number of enterprises in the cultural sector	CC-1	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	100
	Increment in number of mentions of CNH in social media, media, press, etc.	CC-2	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	Mid	Estimations	Yes	50
	Number of users registered in the digital hub or following the social networks (facebook, twitter...)	CC-3	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	100
	Number of posts in the digital hub	CC-4	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	90
	Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level	CC-5	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	90
	Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level (n. and n. of people reached)	CC-6	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Real	Yes	70
	Number of crowdfunding campaigns launched	CC-7	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	Mid	Real	Yes	60
	Number of people trained in traditional skills	CC-8	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	Mid	Estimations	Yes	50
	Number of places involved in the tourism offer	CC-9	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Real	Yes	70
	Distribution of the arrivals along the year (% per month)	CC-10	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Real	Yes	70

Table 9: RACER evaluation of Cultural capital KPIs

The following table shows the final set of cultural capital KPIs, their role in the change of capitals and the type of impact:

CAPITAL	CHANGES IN CAPITALS			Categories	KPI	CODES	Type of impacts
	FROM	TO	SIA				
CULTURAL	CULTURAL	FINANCIAL	ARTS & FESTIVAL	Stocks of cultural capital	Number of enterprises in the cultural sector	CC-1	Economic Impact/ Growth
	CULTURAL	SOCIAL		Increase awareness and ownership of cultural heritage, sense of identity	Increment in number of mentions of CNH in social media, media, press, etc.	CC-2	Social Impact/inclusion
	CULTURAL	SOCIAL			Number of users registered in the digital hub or following the social networks (facebook, twitter...)	CC-3	Social Impact/inclusion
	CULTURAL	SOCIAL			Number of posts in the digital hub	CC-4	Social Impact/inclusion
	CULTURAL	SOCIAL			Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level	CC-5	Social Impact/inclusion
	CULTURAL	SOCIAL/ FINANCIAL	ARTS & FESTIVAL		Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level (n. and n. of people reached)	CC-6	Social Impact/inclusion
	CULTURAL	SOCIAL/ FINANCIAL			Number of crowdfunding campaigns launched	CC-7	Social Impact/inclusion
	CULTURAL	SOCIAL/ FINANCIAL			Valorisation of local traditional skills	Number of people trained in traditional skills	CC-8
	CULTURAL	FINANCIAL		Enlarge the tourism offer and attract different target groups	Number of places involved in the tourism offer	CC-9	Economic Impact/ Growth
	CULTURAL	FINANCIAL			Distribution of the arrivals along the year (% per month)	CC-10	Economic Impact/ Growth

Table 10: Cultural capital KPI

6.1.2 Evaluation procedure

Some of the data are available in a harmonized way at European level and can be found in public data sources such as Eurostat, or estimations can be calculated using specific tools such as Google Trends. Others, due to the specificity of the information required, are difficult to be obtained and should be provided by Replicators, through national or local databases or *ad hoc* measurements. The method used to collect this type of information will be a survey campaign.

KPI	Evaluation procedure
Number of enterprises in the cultural sector	Data obtained from Eurostat dataset: <i>Number and average size of enterprises in the cultural sectors by NACE2 activity</i> http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/cult_ent_num
Number of mentions of CNH in social media, media, press, etc.	Data obtained from Google Trends/Analytics
Number of users registered in the digital hub or following the social networks (facebook, twitter...)	Data provided by RURITAGE Framework
Number of posts in the digital hub	Data provided by RURITAGE Framework
Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level	Data provided by RURITAGE Framework
Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level (n. and n. of people reached)	Data provided by RURITAGE Framework
Number of crowdfunding campaigns launched	Data obtained from main crowdfunding platforms or provided by Replicators
Number of people trained in traditional skills	Data provided by RURITAGE Framework
Number of places involved in the tourism offer	Data provided by RURITAGE Framework
Distribution of the arrivals along the year (% per month)	Local databases and/or information from local public bodies

Table 11: Evaluation procedures

6.2 Natural Capital KPIs

Natural capital is recognized to be strictly related to well-being, as its ecosystem services, such as food, water, landscape and parks, are connected to human health. Natural capital should be therefore seen as an opportunity to improve social and human capitals. Opportunities are also related to the financial capital, as it is demonstrated that there is a return on investment in protected areas, facilitating the support of green jobs. Healthy and resilient ecosystems can provide society with a full range of economically valuable goods and services². The transition to a sustainable growth is correlated to regional attractiveness, quality of life and tourism development. Through 7 KPIs, RURITAGE aims at evaluating the contribution of the natural capital to the human, social and financial capitals.

6.2.1 Selection of the KPIs

The following 7 KPIs have been selected following the RACER method (see Table 12):

² Italian Presidency of the Council of the European Union (2014). Charter of Rome on Natural and Cultural Capital

CAPITAL	KPI	CODES	RELEVANCE		ACCEPTED		CREDIBLE		EASY		ROBUST		RACER Value	
			Meaningful	Comparable	Previously Used	Standard	Unambiguous	Clear Methodology	Availability	Easy to Calculate	Real Data	Applicable to Similar Cases		
NATURAL	Value of ecosystem services	NC-1	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Estimations	Yes	80
	Number and area of designations	NC-2	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Real	Yes	90
	Emission of greenhouse gases	NC-3	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Estimations	Yes	90
	Share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption	NC-4	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Real	Yes	80
	Number of companies and organizations with sustainability certifications and labelling	NC-5	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	80
	Number of shops, restaurants and tourism facilities selling local products (KMO)	NC-6	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Mid	High	Estimations	Yes	65
	Number of "green tourism packages"	NC-7	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Mid	High	Real	Yes	65

Table 12: RACER evaluation of Natural capital KPIs

The following table shows the final set of natural capital KPIs, their role in the change of capitals and the type of impact:

CAPITAL	CHANGES IN CAPITALS			Categories	KPI	CODES	Type of impacts
	FROM	TO	SIA				
NATURAL	NATURAL	HUMAN	FOOD/RESILIENCE	Stocks of natural capital	Value of ecosystem services	NC-1	Environmental Impacts /balance
	NATURAL	SOCIAL			Number and area of designations	NC-2	Environmental Impacts /balance
	NATURAL	HUMAN/SOCIAL			Emission of greenhouse gases	NC-3	Climate Impacts
	NATURAL	FINANCIAL		Promote local business for sustainable production	Share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption	NC-4	Environmental Impacts /balance
	NATURAL	FINANCIAL	FOOD		Number of companies and organizations with sustainability certifications and labelling	NC-5	Environmental Impacts /balance
	NATURAL	FINANCIAL	FOOD		Number of shops, restaurants and tourism facilities selling local products (KMO)	NC-6	Environmental Impacts /balance
	NATURAL	FINANCIAL		Strengthening the tourism sector	Number of "green tourism packages"	NC-7	Economic Impact/ Growth

Table 13: Natural capital KPI

6.2.2 Evaluation procedure

Some of the data are available in a harmonized way at European level and can be found in public data sources, such as Eurostat. Others, due to the specificity of the information required, are difficult to be obtained and should be provided by Replicators, through national or local databases or *ad hoc* measurements. The method used to collect this type of information will be a survey campaign.

KPI	Evaluation procedure
Type of ecosystem services	Specific measure. Data obtained from local databases.
Number and area of designations	National/ local databases
Emission of greenhouse gases	Eurostat dataset: <i>Air emissions accounts by NACE2 activity</i> http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/env_ac_ainah_r2
Share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption	Eurostat dataset: <i>hare of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption by sector</i> http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/sdg_07_40
Number of companies and organizations with sustainability certifications and labelling	National/ local databases
Number of shops, restaurants and tourism facilities selling local products (KMO)	National/ local databases
Number of "green tourism packages"	Local databases

Table 14: Evaluation procedures

6.3 Built capital KPIs

The built capital represents the most tangible part of culture, including buildings and infrastructures. These resources, to be transmitted to future generations, require development strategies which, on the one hand respect their uniqueness and, from the other hand promote sustainable societal, environmental and economic development. Environmental and societal challenges are posing new threats to the management of the built capital, which need to find the balance between heritage preservation and benefits generation for the society. In order to avoid a fixed vision of heritage linked to the past, the built capital should transform its value in accordance to the present and future needs of the society, with the aim of prospering through valorization and revitalization processes. Transition from a built capital to the financial, social, human, natural and cultural capitals is possible through a sustainable approach which promotes the integration and connections between the built and natural heritage, revitalization of the building stock and policies promoting sustainable production, tourism and services.

6.3.1 Selection of the KPIs

Through the following 13 KPIs, RURITAGE aims at evaluating the contribution of the built capital to other capitals (see Table 15):

CAPITAL	KPI	CODES	RELEVANCE		ACCEPTED		CREDIBLE		EASY		ROBUST		RACER Value
			Meaningful	Comparable	Previously Used	Standard	Unambiguous	Clear Methodology	Availability	Easy to Calculate	Real Data	Applicable to Similar Cases	
BUILT	Number of hotspots provided	BC-1	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Real	Yes	70
	Number of people reached through RURITAGE digital tools	BC-2	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	90
	Number of CNH objects mapped trough ATLAS	BC-3	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	90
	Number of beds	BC-4	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Mid	Low	Estimations	Yes	75
	Number of restaurants	BC-5	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Mid	Low	Estimations	Yes	75
	Cycle paths (Km)	BC-6	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Real	Yes	80
	Pedestrian/hiking paths (km)	BC-7	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Real	Yes	80
	Share of people served by public transport services	BC-8	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Estimations	Yes	60
	Number of shared transport services (bike sharing, car sharing, etc.)	BC-9	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Real	Yes	70
	Number of sites accessible by people with disabilities	BC-10	High	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Mid	High	Estimations	Yes	65
	Number of buildings restored/retrofitted	BC-11	High	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Mid	High	Estimations	Yes	65
	Number of reused buildings	BC-12	High	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Mid	High	Estimations	Yes	65
	Number of brands and labels granted for local products and services	BC-13	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	Mid	Estimations	Yes	75
	Number of fairs and tourism events per year related to the promotion of the area and related products	BC-14	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	100
	Number of sites or km of routes provided with signals and explanation panels to help describing the sites and orienteering visitors	BC-15	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	Mid	Estimations	Yes	50

Table 15: RACER evaluation of Built capital KPIs

The following table shows the final set of built capital KPIs, their role in the change of capitals and the type of impact:

CAPITAL	CHANGES IN CAPITALS			Categories	KPI	CODES	Type of impacts
	FROM	TO	SIA				
BUILT	BUILT	SOCIAL		Stocks of built/infrastructure capital	Number of hotspots provided	BC-1	Technological Impacts
	BUILT	SOCIAL			Number of people reached through RURITAGE digital tools	BC-2	Technological Impacts
	BUILT	CULTURAL/ NATURAL			Number of CNH objects mapped trough ATLAS	BC-3	Technological Impacts
	BUILT	FINANCIAL			Number of beds	BC-4	Economic Impact/ Growth
	BUILT	FINANCIAL			Number of restaurants	BC-5	Economic Impact/ Growth
	BUILT	SOCIAL/ NATURAL			Cycle paths (Km)	BC-6	Environmental Impacts /balance
	BUILT	SOCIAL/ NATURAL			Pedestrian/hiking paths (km)	BC-7	Environmental Impacts /balance
	BUILT	SOCIAL			Share of people served by public transport services	BC-8	Environmental Impacts /balance
	BUILT	SOCIAL			Number of shared transport services (bike sharing, car sharing, etc.)	BC-9	Environmental Impacts /balance
	BUILT	SOCIAL/ HUMAN		Promote access and fruition of the CNH of the	Number of sites accessible by people with disabilities	BC-10	Social Impact/inclusion
	BUILT	NATURAL/ FINANCIAL		Eco-restoration and retrofitting of buildings, improving their environmental	Number of buildings restored/retrofitted	BC-11	Environmental Impacts /balance
	BUILT	NATURAL/ FINANCIAL			Number of reused buildings	BC-12	Environmental Impacts /balance
	BUILT	FINANCIAL/ CULTURAL	FOOD	Increase the visibility of the area and the related products	Number of brands and labels granted for local products and services	BC-13	Economic Impact/ Growth
	BUILT	FINANCIAL/ CULTURAL			Number of fairs and tourism events per year related to the promotion of the area and related products	BC-14	Economic Impact/ Growth
	BUILT	NATURAL/ SOCIAL			Number of sites or km of routes provided with signals and explanation panels to help describing the sites and orienteering visitors	BC-15	Economic Impact/ Growth

Table 16: Built capital KPIs

6.3.2 Evaluation procedure

Data on the built capital are difficult to obtain on the local level and should be provided by Replicators, through local databases or *ad hoc* measurements. The method used to collect this type of information will be a survey campaign.

KPI	Evaluation procedure
Number of hotspots provided	Local databases
Number of people reached through RURITAGE digital tools	Data provided by RURITAGE Framework
Number of CNH objects mapped through ATLAS	Data provided by RURITAGE Framework
Number of beds	National/ local databases
Number of restaurants	National/ local databases
Cycle paths (Km)	Local databases/ GIS
Pedestrian/hiking paths (km)	Local databases/GIS
Share of people served by public transport services	Local databases
Number of shared transport services (bike sharing, car sharing, etc.)	Local databases
Number of sites accessible by people with disabilities	Local databases
Number of buildings restored/retrofitted	Local databases
Number of reused buildings	Local databases
Number of brands and labels granted for local products and services	National/ local databases
Number of fairs and tourism events per year related to the promotion of the area and related products	National/ local databases
Number of sites or km of routes provided with signals and explanation panels to help describing the sites and orienteering visitors	National/ local databases

Table 17: Evaluation procedures

6.4 Social Capital KPIs

Communities' quality of life is enhanced and sustained by culture, as this is strictly related to the creation and transmission of values and aptitudes, which are the basis for the construction of social relationships. Sense of integration, empowerment, tolerance to diversity and cooperation are behaviors which are inherited from the past but are being constantly transformed. The local social capital is therefore defined by the level of inclusion and the quality of the relationship of the community. The transition of the social capital to a human capital is enabled by building cultural environments for inclusive, sustainable and human centered development. The promotion of social cooperation leads to creativity and valorization of cultural skills, creating new financial opportunities. Sense of belonging should also be improved through the promotion and increased knowledge of the cultural capital.

6.4.1 Selection of the KPIs

Through the following 7 KPIs, RURITAGE aims at evaluating the contribution of the social capital to human, financial and cultural capitals (see Table 18):

CAPITAL	KPI	CODES	RELEVANCE		ACCEPTED		CREDIBLE		EASY		ROBUST		RACER Value
			Meaningful	Comparable	Previously Used	Standard	Unambiguous	Clear Methodology	Availability	Easy to Calculate	Real Data	Applicable to Similar Cases	
SOCIAL	Number of citizens engagement activities and participants	SC-1	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	Low	Estimations	Yes	45
	Number per type of stakeholder involved (according to the ones defined in D.3.1)	SC-2	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	90
	Number of local associations involved	SC-3	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	90
	Number of participants in formal or informal voluntary activities or active citizenship in the last 12 months	SC-4	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Mid	Mid	Estimations	Yes	60
	Number of immigrants actively engaged in the project and participating to the hub	SC-5	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Real	Yes	70
	Number of projects addressing people with disabilities (n. of projects, and n. of people involved)	SC-6	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Mid	Mid	Real	Yes	70
	Number of disadvantaged people engaged (elderly, migrants, unemployed)	SC-7	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	Low	Estimations	Yes	45

Table 18: RACER evaluation of Social capital KPIs

The following table shows the final set of social capital KPIs, their role in the change of capitals and the type of impact:

CAPITAL	CHANGES IN CAPITALS		Categories	KPI	I codes	Type of impacts
	FROM	TO				
SOCIAL	SOCIAL	CULTURAL/HUMAN	Stocks of social capital	Number of citizens engagement activities and participants	SC-1	Social Impact/inclusion
	SOCIAL	HUMAN		Number per type of stakeholder involved (according to the ones defined in D.3.1)	SC-2	Social Impact/inclusion
	SOCIAL	HUMAN		Number of local associations involved	SC-3	Social Impact/inclusion
	SOCIAL	HUMAN		Number of participants in formal or informal voluntary activities or active citizenship in the last 12 months	SC-4	Social Impact/inclusion
	SOCIAL	HUMAN/FINANCIAL		Number of immigrants actively engaged in the project and participating to the hub	SC-5	Social Impact/inclusion
	SOCIAL	HUMAN		Number of projects addressing people with disabilities (n. of projects, and n. of people involved)	SC-6	Social Impact/inclusion
	SOCIAL	HUMAN		Number of disadvantaged people engaged (elderly, migrants, unemployed)	SC-7	Social Impact/inclusion

Table 19: Social capital KPIs

6.4.2 Evaluation procedure

Most of the data are difficult to obtain on the local level and should be provided by Replicators, through local databases or ad hoc measurements. The method used to collect this type of information will be a survey campaign. Eurostat will be used as a source of information for the KPI related to voluntary activities.

KPI	Evaluation procedure
Number of citizens engagement activities and participants	Local databases
Number per type of stakeholder involved	Ad hoc measurement
Number of local associations involved	Ad hoc measurement
Number of participants in formal or informal voluntary activities or active citizenship in the last 12 months	Eurostat: <i>Participation in formal or informal voluntary activities, or active citizenship</i> http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/ilc_scp20
Number of immigrants actively engaged in the project and participating to the hub	Ad hoc measurement
Number of projects addressing people with disabilities (n. of projects, and n. of people involved)	Local databases
Number of disadvantaged people engaged (elderly, migrants, unemployed)	Ad hoc measurement

Table 20: Evaluation procedures

6.5 Human Capital KPIs

The objective of this set of KPIs is to measure how the skills and abilities of people are used to develop and enhance their resources and to access outside resources and bodies of knowledge to increase their understanding, identify promising practices, and to access data for community-building.

6.5.1 Selection of the KPIs

Through the following 9 KPIs, RURITAGE aims at evaluating the contribution of the human capital to social, financial and cultural capitals (see Table 21):

CAPITAL	KPI	CODES	RELEVANCE		ACCEPTED		CREDIBLE		EASY		ROBUST		RACER Value
			Meaningful	Comparable	Previously Used	Standard	Unambiguous	Clear Methodology	Availability	Easy to Calculate	Real Data	Applicable to Similar Cases	
HUMAN	Level of education	HC-1	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	Mid	Estimations	Yes	85
	Number of recreational facilities/events	HC-2	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	Mid	Estimations	Yes	85
	Number of immigrants involved in educational-training programs	HC-3	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	High	Estimations	Yes	55
	Number of internship for immigrants activated	HC-4	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	High	Estimations	Yes	55
	Number of self-employees	HC-5	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	100
	Number of internship for students	HC-6	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	High	Estimations	Yes	55
	Number of people trained in IT and tourism (in specific SIA)	HC-7	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	High	Estimations	Yes	55
	Number of people involved in professional management training course (summer school and master)	HC-8	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	High	Estimations	Yes	55
	Number of publication as recommendation and guidelines provided	HC-9	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	High	Estimations	Yes	55

Table 21: RACER evaluation of Social capital KPIs

The following table shows the final set of human capital KPIs, their role in the change of capitals and the type of impact:

CAPITAL	CHANGES IN CAPITALS			Categories	KPI	CODES	Type of impacts
	FROM	TO	SIA				
HUMAN	HUMAN	CULTURAL/FINANCIAL		Stocks of human capital	Level of education	HC-1	Social Impact/inclusion
					Number of recreational facilities/events	HC-2	Social Impact/inclusion
	HUMAN	FINANCIAL/SOCIAL	MIGRANTS	Foster innovation in local business and start-ups (organizational, process and products innovation, etc.) Set-up and growth of companies	Number of immigrants involved in educational-training programs	HC-3	Social Impact/inclusion
	HUMAN	FINANCIAL/SOCIAL	MIGRANTS		Number of internship for immigrants activated	HC-4	Social Impact/inclusion
	HUMAN	FINANCIAL			Number of self-employees	HC-5	Economic Impact/ Growth
	HUMAN	FINANCIAL/SOCIAL		Improvement of IT skills of citizens (different groups)	Number of internship for students	HC-6	Social Impact/inclusion
	HUMAN	FINANCIAL/SOCIAL			Number of people trained in IT and tourism (in specific SIA)	HC-7	Technological Impacts
	HUMAN	FINANCIAL		Improve the CNH management system of the local authorities (guidelines, training, etc.)	Number of people involved in professional management training course (summer school and master)	HC-8	Organizational Impacts
	HUMAN	FINANCIAL			Number of publication as recommendation and guidelines provided	HC-9	Organizational Impacts

Table 22: Social capital KPIs

6.5.2 Evaluation procedure

Some of the data due to the specificity of the information required, are difficult to be obtained and should be provided by Replicators, through national or local databases or *ad hoc* measurements. The method used to collect this type of information will be a survey campaign.

KPI	Evaluation procedure
Level of education	Eurostat dataset: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/tgs00091
Number of recreational facilities/events	Questionnaire
Number of immigrants involved in educational-training programs	Questionnaire
Number of internship for immigrants activated	Questionnaire
Number of self-employees	Eurostat dataset: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/lfst_r_e2sganu
Number of internships for students	Questionnaire
Number of people trained in IT and tourism (in specific SIA)	Questionnaire
Number of people involved in professional management training course (summer school and master)	Questionnaire
Number of publications as recommendation and guidelines provided	Questionnaire

Table 23: Evaluation procedures

6.6 Financial Capital KPIs

It has been recognized that culture is playing an increasingly role as productive sector in local economies, being a driver of economic growth, job generation and innovation. Cultural and creative activities and industries can translate into increased social and human capitals. Beyond the capacity of creating employment, cultural activities foster creative expressions and invest in new entrepreneurial skills, contributing to the diversification of economies and enlarging the customer choices. The transition from a financial capital to a more social and human capital is based on the synergies with sectors related to culture and innovation, such as, among others, tourism, information and communication technologies and local production.

6.6.1 Selection of the KPIs

Through the following 5 KPIs, RURITAGE aims at evaluating the contribution of the financial capital to social and human capitals (see Table 24):

CAPITAL	KPI	CODES	RELEVANCE		ACCEPTED		CREDIBLE		EASY		ROBUST		RACER Value
			Meaningful	Comparable	Previously Used	Standard	Unambiguous	Clear Methodology	Availability	Easy to Calculate	Real Data	Applicable to Similar Cases	
FINANCIAL	Nights spent at tourist accommodation establishments	FC-1	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	100
	Year revenues per sector/municipality (in specific SIA)	FC-2	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	Mid	Estimations	Yes	50
	Number of PPPs set and signed	FC-3	High	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	High	Estimations	Yes	55
	Unemployment rate (%)	FC-4	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	100
	Number of start-ups and spin-off created / Birth of enterprises	FC-5	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	100
	Number of companies supported in defining new business models and innovative processes of production	FC-6	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	High	High	Real	Yes	90

Table 24: RACER evaluation of financial capitals

The following table shows the final set of financial capital KPIs, their role in the change of capitals and the type of impact:

CAPITAL	CHANGES IN CAPITALS		Categories	KPI	I codes	Type of impacts
	FROM	TO				
FINANCIAL	FINANCIAL	SOCIAL	Stocks of financial capital	Nights spent at tourist accommodation establishments	FC-1	Economic Impact/ Growth
	FINANCIAL	HUMAN/SOCIAL		Year revenues per sector/municipality (in specific SIA)	FC-2	Economic Impact/ Growth
	FINANCIAL	HUMAN/SOCIAL		Number of PPPs set and signed	FC-3	Social Impact/inclusion
	FINANCIAL	HUMAN		Unemployment rate (%)	FC-4	Social Impact/inclusion
	FINANCIAL	HUMAN	Foster innovation in local business and start-ups (organizational, process and products innovation, etc.)	Number of start-ups and spin-off created / Birth of enterprises	FC-5	Economic Impact/ Growth
	FINANCIAL	HUMAN		Number of companies supported in defining new business models and innovative processes of production	FC-6	Economic Impact/ Growth

Table 25: Financial capital KPIs

6.6.2 Evaluation procedure

Some of the data are available in a harmonized way at European level and can be found in public data sources, such as Eurostat. Others, due to the specificity of the information required, are difficult to be obtained and should be provided by Replicators, through national or local databases or *ad hoc* measurements. The method used to collect this type of information will be a survey campaign.

KPI	Evaluation procedure
Nights spent at tourist accommodation establishments	Eurostat dataset: <i>Nights spent at tourist accommodation establishments by degree of urbanisation and by NUTS 2 regions</i> http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/tour_occ_nin2d "
Year revenues per sector/municipality (in specific SIA)	Local databases
Number of PPPs set and signed	Local databases
Unemployment rate	Eurostat dataset: <i>Unemployment rates by sex, age and degree of urbanisation</i> http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/lfst_r_urgau "
Number of start-ups and spin-off created / Birth of enterprises	National/ local databases
Number of companies supported in defining new business models and innovative processes of production	Local databases

Table 25: Evaluation procedures

7. Conclusions and next steps

Key performance indicators are valuable pointers for establishing future rural strategies as well as for evaluating project impacts. However, nowadays, no standard has been developed for evaluating heritage-led practices in rural areas and it does not exist any broadly accepted indicator system covering the SIAs of RURITAGE. As a result, an on-site guided tailored procedure has been established in order to define the KPIs which will take part of the evaluation plan of the project. On the other hand, in such complex project as RURITAGE, there are many connections among tasks, in special among issues linked to the evaluation. Hence, this report is focus on describing the KPIs selection, fine tuning and upgrading in order to be a working document for RURITAGE partners mainly involved in WP1 and WP5 to start defining the link between Role Models and Replicators.

Data curation and aggregation, in the sense of organising and integrating data from different sources, will be developed in Task 4.2. Other elements of data curation, as determining what information is worth to be saved and for how long, are mainly intended when dealing with big data and do not apply in this case. The FAIR³ Data Management Plan (deliverable D8.4) includes further details about the kind and amount of expected data related to the KPIs and Monitoring tasks.

As previously mentioned, the process of KPI selection and tailoring has determined what indicators should be monitored, but it could produce some sideways effects. While maintaining the widest scope of indicators to capture as much as possible impacts of rural regeneration action plans, some indicators could be hard to find significant data for a specific local SIA. In those cases, and according to the 'Critical risk for implementation' table, searching for complementary or national/internationally recognized alternative sources of information will be applied upon consensus between KFPs and Rs.

³ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable.

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